

SANITATION: SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE

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[Abstract: Cleanliness and Sanitation is a major issue in the development discussions owing to its contribution to sustainable human development. In the present day market economy wherein competition and the technological strength decide economic progress. In a market based competitive economy ignoring environment and nature related life style is common. Environmental imbalance and deterioration of quality of natural resources coupled with transformation of cultural practices and human behaviour calls for an attention of policy makers, and institutional intervention in health, sanitation and hygiene. And they involve transaction cost, but for social benefit. Therefore, issues related it needs to be analyzed with both economic and sociological perspectives. Such an attempt is made in this paper, which claims more relevant in the context of Swacha Bharath agenda]

Key Words: Sanitation; Drinking Water; Health; Hygiene; Cost-benefits; Cost-effective; Culture , Swacha Bharath

Introduction

Social welfare is the main concern of the development theories in which sustainability has been the major focus. In the recent years, recognizing the importance of maintaining environmental balance, economists analyzed issues related to resource and resource use pattern including the cultural resources. The concept, Sustainable development focus mainly on environmental balance in terms of healthy utilization of natural resources and managing activities centred on it, thereby to preserve the environmental quality and behaviour. Recently, theoreticians and policy makers realized that the culture and human behaviour play significant role in sustaining environment and the development process. Human capital formation theories advocate for a sustainable, healthy human resource development. In this context, education,

training/skill formation, and health sectors gained importance. These three sectors related to Human Resources development are inter-linked forming the base for the social welfare oriented development thinking.

Health sector transformation from tradition to technology based modern has been evaluated variously and no doubt the achievements made in this sector is remarkable. However, the over all developmental efforts and approaches resulted in expanded market, lead to several challenges. Environmental quality deterioration, abrupt resource extraction and the resulting externalities have become a major threat. More specifically, safe drinking water supply and sanitation has become a major challenge in the recent years. Diagnosing the sociological and economic perspectives of this challenge is a major task among the governments and civil society organisations all over the world.

With this backdrop, this paper attempts to explore the economics of sanitation sociology for sustainable social welfare.

Objectives

The main aim of this paper is to assess the applicability of a recently developed and widely supported economic evaluation framework to appraise alternative water and sanitation interventions, and make recommendations for those wishing to conduct economic evaluations in this area of research. The specific objectives of the paper are;

1. To analyse the socio-cultural practices of Indian traditions in relation to sanitation.
2. To examine the transformations of such sanitation practices in the modern market economy and their challenges.
3. To analyse the Economics of health and sanitation and the role of government and NGO interventions in this sectors

Health and Sanitation

Health and sanitation is an important issue in relation to social welfare. It has been a culture encompassing public health and hygiene. Environmental science with market failure and externality concepts invite institutional principles to manage sanitation for sustainable society. Indian traditional practices and cultural celebrations have health dimensions. Health services and food practices were closely related to nature. Our traditional folk medicines were directly derived from the nature around. Medicinal plants were known to everyone, and even

illiterates knowledge on natural medicines was of high level. Growing medicinal plants (Eg. Tulsi plant) around the residence is a significance of sanitation and hygiene. Vegetables and fruits grown only for household consumption (not for competitive market) using organic manures were of nutritional rich. Many of the traditional socio-cultural practices were sustainable in nature having more concern on sanitation and hygiene. Indian traditions, socio-cultural practices gave utmost importance for sanitation, but now in the changed context of market economy, sociology of sanitation has to be viewed from economic perspectives. This is mainly because, negative externalities of many practices and behaviour and the extent of institutional interventions may be government or non-government.

Economics of Sanitation

Different branches of economics like Health Economics, Environmental economics and Welfare economics, and economics of Human Resource are concerned with health, sanitation and hygiene. Economics, essentially deals with the allocation of scarce resources among competing alternatives, aiming at maximizing outcome of human interest (e.g. profit, health, HRD or Social welfare). In the health sector, policy makers and programme executives are constantly faced with economic decisions, related to how to spend a limited budget and have the biggest impact on health? The technique of economic evaluation can contribute to these decisions by providing information on the costs and benefits of alternative interventions, summarizing information in a cost-effectiveness or cost-benefit ratio. In addition to the information, it helps to bring elements of transparency and objectivity to policy making. Economic analysis of Water and sanitation provide a framework application of economic principles to appropriate resource allocation, which in fact is a major challenge.. The challenge is because, the existing economic evaluation methods are to evaluate the health services provided, focusing on cost and benefits of the health services in general.

Health Economics analyzing the relationship between health and other goods, recently have become very popular (Kenneth Arrow-1963). Health economics is concerned with issues related to efficiency, effectiveness, value and behaviour in the production and consumption of health and health care services. Health economists show interest in studying the functioning of healthcare systems and health-affecting behaviors such as safe drinking water, sanitation and other related practices.

Factors that distinguish health economics from other branches include extensive government and Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs) intervention,

intractable uncertainty in several dimensions, asymmetric information, and barriers to entry, externalities and the presence of middleman. Health economists evaluate multiple types of financial information - costs, benefit, charges/price and expenditures. It is essential to weigh up costs against benefits and in doing so one of the more difficult problems is to come up with a monetary measure for different benefits. One should remember here that ‘prevention is better than cure’, which emphasizes more on environment and sanitation.

Like several environmental interventions aimed at improving or sustaining health, water supply and sanitation interventions are different. The differences noticed are;

- They are more likely to be regulatory in nature (such as the meeting of quality criteria)
- they involve cross-sector collaboration and are often financed by non-health agencies (Varley et al. 1998)
- They provide large non-health benefits (such as time saving, increasing amenity etc.) which are important to consider (Hutton 2000)
- They are less amenable to controlled trials to evaluate effectiveness (Blum and Feachem 1983)
- Different studies have reported wide ranges of effect (Esrey et al. 1985) leading to difficulties in generalising results between different settings.

The implication of these aspects is that appropriate methods for evaluating water and sanitation interventions have remained underdeveloped, and subsequently there are few published studies that have dealt with the economics of water and sanitation interventions in a comprehensive or satisfactory way (Hutton 2000).

Another particular challenge faced in implementing water and sanitation interventions in developing countries is that the expenditure patterns required to meet current guidelines and standards are unrealistic in many developing countries (WHO 1997). This requires many resource-poor countries to make choices over which quality standards they should meet using a risk-benefit or economic evaluation approach, since meeting some quality standards may be less expensive and/or have a larger health effect than others. Again, there is remarkably limited evidence on the cost-effectiveness of water and sanitation interventions to make these choices (Hutton 2000).

Environmental health interventions (mostly prevention) differ from core health services. It is for these reasons most research studies on on primary health-care interventions,

focused on several economic aspects of water supply, water quality and sanitation interventions, including costs, cost effectiveness, willingness to pay, and cost-of-illness. However, few studies measured the costs and benefits of alternative interventions to provide policy makers with the information to choose the most efficient intervention from the viewpoint of society or the health sector. Generally, it would seem that there has been inadequate attention to economic issues in water and sanitation interventions.

Water Supply and Sanitation

Economic benefits of investing in water and sanitation are considerable, they include an overall estimated gain of 1.5 per cent of global GDP and a US\$ 4.3 return for every dollar invested in water and sanitation services, due to reduced health care costs for individuals and society, and greater productivity and involvement in the workplace through better access to facilities

Diarrhoea disease ranked fourth as a cause of death (around 5% of total death). Poor water supply, sanitation and hygiene are the major factor responsible for such death. Disease related to poor quality water supply, sanitation and hygiene have significant economic impact on society.

Costs on this include both public and private cost. Private costs include opportunity costs in addition to the direct costs in terms of negative impact on household income. Studies on cost-benefits of improving water and sanitation services show that both interventions are highly economically viable.

Changing social norms at community level is a major determinate of achieving sustainable sanitation. Poverty eradication, which is a major challenge to the underdeveloped/developing countries with high population, and it cannot be eliminated beyond a level unless sanitation is sustained.

Significant achievements were made by the end of the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) era, but according to an estimate 663 million people still lack access to an “improved” source of drinking-water. Many more still lack access to “safe” drinking-water, with at least 1.9 billion people relying on an unimproved source or an improved source that is basically contaminated. Through the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of United Nation's (U.N), countries around the world have expressed strong political will to ensure not only that a drinking-water service is extended to less served populations, but also that this drinking-water

is universally safe. This is expressed in Goal six of the SDGs, with Target 6.1 stating “By 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking-water for all”.

However, as land-use pressures and competition for limited water resources intensify through population growth, it is clear that the entire water cycle needs to be managed as a whole to ensure that limited freshwater resources within are protected. Unless managed effectively, these pressures may affect surface-water quality both directly and indirectly, with adverse effects on public health.

One of the targets of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of the United Nations (UN) was to cut by half the proportion of people without sustainable access to drinking-water by 2015 (UN, 2015). This target – measured by the proxy indicator “improved” water supply – was reached ahead of schedule in 2010, with 91.0 per cent of the world’s population using an improved drinking-water source (WHO & UNICEF, 2015). But, important challenges remain, as 663 million people worldwide still lack access to improved water sources, and 159 million of these people rely on untreated surface water, which poses even greater health risks than other water sources. Also, there are significant access disparities both among and within countries. For example, in some countries, less than half of the population has access to improved sources, and access rates are significantly lower in rural areas than in urban areas. Improved sources have, by definition, been designed to be protected from contamination; however, water from improved sources is not always safe to drink (WHO & UNICEF, 2015). Hence, using an improved drinking-water source as an indicator for the use of safe water may overestimate the actual proportion of the global population using safe water (Onda, LoBuglio & Bartram, 2012).

The UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) go beyond access to improved water supply (UN, 2016). The SDGs call for achieving universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking-water for all. They also call for water quality to be improved by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater, and at least doubling water recycling and safe reuse globally.

Water quality is often seen as an “end of pipe” issue, to be managed by water treatment before delivery to consumers, or even by treatment in consumers’ households. However, a combination of barriers throughout the water-supply system is a fundamental requirement for safe drinking-water. These barriers can include:

- Selection and protection of water sources;

- Optimization of abstraction and treatment; and
- Prevention of deterioration of water quality in the distribution system, including installations in buildings.

A multiple-barrier approach is particularly important when the source water contains a wide range of microbial and chemical hazards, as is often the case with surface water

Status of water Supply in India

In 2021, a significant portion of India's rural habitations (79.11%) had access to potable drinking water supply greater than 40 liters per capita per day, though 2.17 per cent still faced water quality issues. The National Sample Survey Office (NSSO) 78th round (2020-21) found that only 36.6 percent of Indian households had piped water, with a major rural-urban gap (25% vs. 61.4%). Hand pumps and tube wells remained the most common water source, especially in rural areas. Among the urban households 61.4 per cent and only 25.0 percent of the rural households had piped water. More common in urban areas, where 9.8 percent of households relied on Bottled water in 2020-21.

Swacha Bharath Programme

Democratic India made several efforts to improve the sanitation and for the provision of safe drinking water. According to the Census-1981, the rural sanitation coverage in India was only 1.0 percent.

The first nationwide programme with a focus on sanitation was the Central Rural Sanitation Programme (CRSP), which was started in 1986 to provide sanitation facilities in rural areas. Later, in 1999, CRSP was restructured and launched as the Total Sanitation Campaign (TSC). While CRSP was a supply-driven infrastructure-oriented programme based on subsidy, TSC was a demand-driven, community-led, project-based programme organized around the district as the unit.

In India, only 22.0 percent of the rural families had access to toilets in 2001. It increased further to 32.7 percent by 2011. Total Sanitation Campaign was renamed Nirmal Bharat Abhiyan (NBA) in 2001, to accelerate the sanitation coverage in rural areas through saturation approach and by enhancing incentives for Individual Household Latrines (IHHL).

During 1980s, the Integrated Low-Cost Sanitation Scheme provided subsidies for households to build low-cost toilets. Additionally, the National Slum Development Project and its replacement programme, the Valmiki Ambedkar Awas Yojana launched in 2001, were programmes that aimed to construct community toilets for slum populations. In 2008, the

National Urban Sanitation Policy (NUSP) was announced to manage human excreta and associated public health and environmental impacts.

On October 2, 2014, the Swachh Bharat Mission was launched with two components: Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin/Rural) and Swachh Bharat Mission (Urban), to focus on rural and urban sanitation, respectively. While the rural component of the Mission is implemented under the Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation, the urban one is implemented by the Ministry of Housing and Urban Affairs. In 2015, the Sub-Group of Chief Ministers on *Swachh Bharat Abhiyaan* under NITI Aayog had observed that the key difference between SBM and previous programmes was in the efforts to attract more partners to supplement public sector investment towards sanitation.

The Indian government's expenditure on the Swachh Bharat Mission has been substantial, with the Swachh Bharat Mission (Urban) II, allocation being ₹30,980.20 crore for 2021-2026 and the Swachh Bharat Mission (Gramin) (SBM-G), Phase II (2020-2025) having an outlay of ₹1.41 lakh crore. The combined allocation for the mission in the 2025 budget was ₹12,192 crore, comprising ₹5,000 crore for the urban component and ₹7,192 crore for the rural component.

**Table-1: Progress of Swachh Bharath Mission in terms of Funds allocation
(Rs. In Crore)**

Year	Funds Allocated to SBM-G	Funds released to state/UTs Under SBM-G	Funds spent on IEC at Central Level (%)
2014-15	2850.00	2730.31	97.32
2015-16	6525.00	6362.96	160.50
2016-17	10500.00	10271.96	234.86
2017-18	16948.27	16610.87	320.16
2018-19	23176.23	21493.12	114.04
2019-20	11938.22	10992.28	38.01
2020-21	6000.00	3892.18	16.14
2021-22	6000.00	2058.16	3.23
Total	83937.72	74411.84	984.26

Source; Swachha Bharath Mission, Reports

Conclusion

Health, sanitation and hygiene assume importance in the sustainable development and the present status of this is very low especially in backward Countries. Both government and Non-government agencies are working towards this, in local and international level. Deterioration of Health, sanitation and hygiene conditions are due to various reasons and mainly changed human practices. In setting them right, economics has to play a role. Economic impact of culture and human practices on sanitation and health and cost-benefits of institutional interventions are of more significance. Environment perspective, health perspective and civilization perspective demand improved sanitation and hygiene, wherein government intervention through appropriate policy frame is essential. Framing policy has to consider both economic and sociological dimension of sanitation.

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